

Stress tolerance— adverse soils

Promising salt-tolerant F₁ anther culture derivatives (ACDs)

R. K. Singh and B. Mishra, Central Soil Salinity Research Institute, Karnal 132001, India; and D. Senadhira, IIRRI

We evaluated 15 selected ACDs developed at IIRRI (IR51500-AC-17, IR51491-AC-1, IR51491-AC-5, IR51491-AC-6, IR51491-AC-7, IR51485-AC-2, IR51485-AC-3, IR51485-AC-4, AC6533-3, AC6533-4, AC6534-1, AC6534-3, AC6534-4, AC6549, AC6554-2) and tolerant check variety CSR10 for salt tolerance.

Field trials were laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications at two sites with different salt stress levels. Gudha had a pH₂ of 10.32 and Mundlana had a pH₂ of 8.23-9.45 and ECe 3.88-10.74 dS/m. Chemical amendments were not applied to the soil.

Forty-day-old seedlings (raised in better soils) were transplanted at 15 × 15-cm spacing. Three doses of N (150 kg/ha total) and one basal dose of Zn (5.75 kg/ha) were applied.

ACDs differed significantly in 50% flowering, plant height, tillers/plant, and productivity (see table). Many derivatives

ANOVA and promising entries of F₁ ACDs.

Promising entry	Days to flowering	Plant height (m)	Panicle bearing tillers (no./plant)	Yield (kg/3 m ²)
<i>Gudha</i>				
AC6533-3	135.0	0.57	7.3	0.446
AC6549	135.7	0.66	6.0	0.270
AC6534-1	133.0	0.73	6.3	0.266
CSR10	103.7	0.57	9.6	0.453
<i>Mundlana</i>				
AC6534-1	115.3	1.02	11.3	1.707
AC6534-4	117.0	0.97	10.3	1.590
IR1500-AC-17	125.3	0.99	12.3	1.420
CSR10	98.7	0.66	11.6	1.413
<i>Average</i>				
AC6534-1	124.2	0.88	8.8	0.986
AC6534-4	125.7	0.85	8.6	0.911
IR1500-AC-17	132.7	0.79	11.1	0.727
CSR10	101.2	0.62	10.6	0.933

SV	DF	MS ^a			
		Days to flowering	Plant height (m)	Panicle bearing tillers (no./plant)	Yield (kg/3 m ²)
Replications within locations	4	11.9	0.036	4.11	0.065
Genotypes (g)	15	500.6*	0.048*	15.20*	0.536*
Locations(1)	1	2175.0*	4.472*	201.30*	8.239*
g × l	15	57.6*	0.031*	3.70	0.463*
Residual error	60	3.9	0.006	3.60	0.049
LSD					
g		1.9	0.085	1.84	0.214
l		0.7	0.030	0.65	0.075
g × l		2.7	0.120	—	0.303

^a * = significant at p = 0.05.

exhibited salt tolerance at par with that of CSR 10.

Delayed flowering and maturity of ACDs were the most undesirable traits compared with the early heading and

maturity of check CSR10. We selected AC6534-1 and AC6534-4 as promising lines for our breeding strategies to enhance the salt-affected soil productivity. □

Integrated germplasm improvement—irrigated

Performance of Basmati rices in Rajasthan

R. S. Tripathi and R. Pandya, Agriculture Research Station, Banswara 327001, India

Traditional Basmati rices remain popular in Banswara although they yield poorly and are prone to lodging.

We conducted trials for Basmati rices from 1988 to 1990. Mahi Sugandha, a semidwarf, photoperiod-insensitive variety with basmati-type grains, yielded the most at 5.6 t/ha. Basmati 370 averaged 3.7 t/ha and Kali Kamod, a

popular variety with short, slender grain and strong aroma, 3.5 t/ha (Table 1). Mahi Sugandha significantly

outyielded other varieties, including Basmati 370, in All India Coordinated Trials during kharif 1990. Mahi Sugandha

Table 1. Mean performance of Basmati cultures in Rajasthan, India, 1988-90.

Variety	Av yield (t/ha)	% increase over Basmati 370	Days to flowering	Plant height (cm)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Panicle length (cm)
Mahi Sugandha	5.6	50.6	102	92	489	31.7
IET8580	4.9	30.9	98	84	385	25.0
IET8581	4.3	15.1	99	74	455	20.7
IET8365	3.5	—	100	91	450	24.7
IET10366	3.4	—	99	111	356	27.0
IET10651	3.5	—	121	102	210	23.5
Kali Kamod (c)	3.5	—	105	118	275	21.6
Basmati 370 (c)	3.7	—	107	125	280	27.2